

COMPARISON OF THE EFFECTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC AND OPEN SURGERY ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN COLORECTAL CANCER PATIENTS

Keywords

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ABSTRACT
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To evaluate health-related quality of life (HRQoL) and identify factors associated with general health status in patients undergoing curative surgery for colorectal cancer using the European Organization for Cancer Research and Treatment Quality of Life Questionnaire-Correction 30 (EORTC QLQ-C30). This single-center cross-sectional study included 54 patients who underwent curative surgery for histopathologically confirmed colorectal adenocarcinoma between January 2024 and December 2025. Quality of life (HRQoL) was assessed using the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire. Demographic, surgical, stoma-related, and oncological treatment characteristics were analyzed. Univariate analyses, multivariate linear regression, and multivariate logistic regression were performed to identify factors associated with Global Health Status (GHS). The mean age was 65.7 ± 11.7 years, and 55.6% of the patients were male. The mean GHS score was 66.0 ± 18.8 . Among the functional domains, cognitive function showed the highest score (85.5 ± 20.0), while emotional function showed the lowest score (61.4 ± 29.0). Fatigue, financial difficulties, and pain constituted the greatest symptom burden. GHS scores were significantly higher in patients younger than 65 years compared to older patients (72.2 ± 16.6 vs. 61.1 ± 19.2 , $p=0.027$). No significant difference was observed according to gender, stoma status, surgical category, adjuvant chemotherapy, or neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy. In multivariate linear regression, no independent predictor of GHS was identified. However, multivariate logistic regression showed that being 65 years of age or older was independently associated with poor quality of life (OR 3.67, 95% CI 1.10–12.25, $p=0.035$). Quality of life after curative surgery for colorectal cancer was satisfactory. Advanced age was the only independent predictor of impaired quality of life; surgical procedure, stoma formation, and oncological treatments were not significantly associated with global health status. Age-specific supportive strategies may improve long-term survival outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer remains one of the most commonly diagnosed malignant tumors worldwide and, despite significant advances in screening, surgical techniques, and systemic therapies, is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths. Recent advances in multidisciplinary treatment have led to improved survival rates and shifted the focus from survival rates alone to the long-term functional outcomes and quality of life of surviving patients^{1,2}.

Surgical resection remains the cornerstone of curative treatment for colorectal cancer. Depending on the tumor's location and stage, patients may undergo various surgical procedures, ranging from right hemicolectomy to low anterior resection or abdominoperineal resection. In addition, some patients may require the creation of a temporary or permanent stoma. While these approaches are effective in achieving oncological control, they can also affect daily functioning, body image, social interactions, and quality of life. Consequently, the assessment of patient-reported outcomes has become an increasingly important component of colorectal cancer treatment^{1,2}.

Quality of life is a multidimensional concept that encompasses physical, emotional, cognitive, and social functioning, as well as treatment-related symptoms. Previous studies have shown that colorectal cancer patients may experience persistent fatigue, pain, bowel dysfunction, sleep disturbances, and financial difficulties even after successful oncological treatment^{3,4}.

In addition, factors such as advanced age, stoma creation, and adjuvant therapies have been reported to affect quality-of-life outcomes; however, the current evidence remains inconsistent⁵⁻⁸.

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The European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire—Core 30 (EORTC QLQ-C30) is one of the most widely used and validated tools for assessing quality of life in cancer patients⁶.

This questionnaire provides a comprehensive assessment of general health status, functional domains, and symptom burden, enabling standardized comparisons across different patient groups and treatment strategies⁹⁻¹¹.

Although the number of studies evaluating quality of life following colorectal cancer treatment is steadily increasing, real-world data examining the combined effects of surgical characteristics, stoma creation, and oncological treatments remain limited. Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess quality of life outcomes using the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire in patients who underwent surgery for colorectal cancer and to identify factors associated with global health status.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Patient Population

This single-center, cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Pamukkale University Faculty of Medicine. The study included patients who underwent curative surgery for histopathologically confirmed colorectal adenocarcinoma between January 2024 and December 2025 and attended outpatient follow-up examinations.

Adult patients (≥ 18 years of age) who underwent curative-intent surgery for histopathologically confirmed colon or rectal adenocarcinoma and completed the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire-Core 30 (EORTC QLQ-C30) were included in the study. Patients with disease recurrence, metastatic disease at the time of questionnaire administration, severe cognitive impairment preventing completion of the questionnaire, or incomplete questionnaire data were excluded.

Demographic characteristics such as age and gender, surgical procedure, stoma status, and oncological treatment history were obtained from hospital records. Surgical procedures were classified as low anterior resection (LAR), right hemicolectomy, abdominoperineal resection (APR), and Hartmann procedure. Due to the limited number of patients undergoing abdominoperineal resection and Hartmann

procedure, surgical procedures were classified as colon surgery and rectal surgery for comparative analysis. Right hemicolectomy was classified as colon surgery, while low anterior resection and abdominoperineal resection were classified as rectal surgery. Patients were also classified according to the presence of ileostomy or colostomy and whether they received adjuvant chemotherapy, neoadjuvant chemotherapy, or neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy.

The study was approved by the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Pamukkale University Faculty of Medicine (Approval No. E-60116787-020-778517; Approval Date: 14 October 2025).

Quality-of-Life Assessment

Quality of life was assessed using the validated European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire-Core 30 (EORTC QLQ-C30), a cancer-specific instrument consisting of 30 items. The questionnaire comprises five functional scales (physical, role, emotional, cognitive, and social functioning), three symptom scales (fatigue, nausea/vomiting, and pain), five single-item symptom measures (dyspnea, insomnia, appetite loss, diarrhea, and financial difficulties), and a global health status/quality-of-life scale.

Raw scores were linearly transformed to a 0–100 scale according to the EORTC QLQ-C30 Scoring Manual. Higher scores on the functional and global health status scales indicate better functioning and quality of life, whereas higher scores on the symptom scales indicate greater symptom burden.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm SD or median (minimum–maximum), and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test.

Comparisons between groups were performed using Student's *t*-test or Mann–Whitney *U* test, while ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis test was used for multiple-group comparisons. Categorical variables were analyzed using the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test.

Factors associated with Global Health Status (GHS) were first evaluated by univariate analysis. Age, sex, stoma status,

surgical category, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy were then entered into multivariable linear regression. In addition, GHS was dichotomized (cutoff: 70 points) and analyzed using multivariable logistic regression. Results are presented as β coefficients or odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). A two-sided $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 54 patients who underwent surgical treatment for colorectal cancer completed the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire and were included in the analysis. The mean age was 65.7 ± 11.7 years, and 30 patients (55.6%) were male. The most frequently performed procedure was low anterior resection (75.9%), followed by right hemicolectomy (18.5%). Ileostomy and colostomy were present in 29.6% and 7.4% of patients, respectively. Adjuvant chemotherapy was administered to 75.9% of patients, while neoadjuvant chemotherapy and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy were administered to 16.7% and 29.6% of patients, respectively. (Table 1)

The mean global health status score was 66.0 ± 18.8 . Among functional domains, cognitive function showed the highest score (85.5 ± 20.0), while emotional function received the lowest score (61.4 ± 29.0). Among symptom scales, fatigue (45.3 ± 24.4), financial difficulties (44.4 ± 33.6), and pain (41.4 ± 24.2) represented the most significant symptom burden.

Univariate analyses evaluating the effects of adjuvant chemotherapy, neoadjuvant chemotherapy, neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, ileostomy, and colostomy on general health status and baseline functional scales did not reveal statistically significant differences (all $p > 0.05$). (Table 2)

Global health status scores were compared according to demographic, surgical, and oncological characteristics. Patients under 65 years of age had significantly higher general health status scores than those 65 years and older (72.2 ± 16.6 vs. 61.1 ± 19.2 , $p = 0.027$). No significant difference in general health status was observed according to gender, stoma status, surgical procedure, adjuvant chemotherapy, or neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy (all $p > 0.05$). (Table 3)

Multivariate linear regression analysis was performed to identify independent determinants of global health status (Table 4). Variables included age, gender, stoma status, surgical procedure, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy. None of the evaluated variables were independently associated with global health status. Although increasing age showed a trend towards decreasing global health scores ($\beta = -0.38$, 95% CI -0.84 to 0.07 , $p = 0.099$), this association was not statistically significant. Gender, stoma status, surgical procedure, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy were not significantly associated with global health status.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n=54)

Variable	Value
Age, years (mean \pm SD)	65.7 ± 11.7
Male sex, n (%)	30 (55.6)
Female sex, n (%)	24 (44.4)
Low anterior resection (LAR), n (%)	41 (75.9)
Right hemicolectomy, n (%)	10 (18.5)
Abdominoperineal resection (APR), n (%)	2 (3.7)
Hartmann procedure, n (%)	1 (1.9)
Ileostomy, n (%)	16 (29.6)
Colostomy, n (%)	4 (7.4)
Adjuvant chemotherapy, n (%)	41 (75.9)
Neoadjuvant chemotherapy, n (%)	9 (16.7)
Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, n (%)	16 (29.6)

Table 2. EORTC QLQ-C30 Scores

Scale	Mean \pm SD
Global health status	66.0 \pm 18.8
Physical functioning	67.0 \pm 21.8
Role functioning	64.2 \pm 30.1
Emotional functioning	61.4 \pm 29.0
Cognitive functioning	85.5 \pm 20.0
Social functioning	65.1 \pm 25.5
Fatigue	45.3 \pm 24.4
Nausea/Vomiting	12.7 \pm 21.7
Pain	41.4 \pm 24.2
Dyspnea	19.1 \pm 27.9
Insomnia	25.3 \pm 34.8
Appetite loss	21.6 \pm 33.1
Diarrhea	31.5 \pm 36.9
Financial difficulties	44.4 \pm 33.6

Table 3. Factors Associated with Global Health Status Score

Variable	n	Global Health Score (Mean \pm SD)	p value
Age <65 years	24	72.2 \pm 16.6	0.027
Age \geq 65 years	30	61.1 \pm 19.2	
Male	30	65.6 \pm 20.0	0.829
Female	24	66.7 \pm 17.5	
Stoma present	19	68.9 \pm 16.2	0.394
No stoma	35	64.5 \pm 20.1	
Rectal surgery (LAR/APR)	43	66.5 \pm 19.1	0.738
Colon surgery (Right hemicolectomy)	10	64.2 \pm 19.3	
Adjuvant chemotherapy	41	67.1 \pm 17.5	0.548
No adjuvant chemotherapy	13	62.8 \pm 23.0	
Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy	16	69.8 \pm 16.9	0.322
No neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy	38	64.5 \pm 19.5	

Table 4. Multivariable Linear Regression Analysis for Global Health Status Score

Variable	β coefficient	95% CI	p value
Age (years)	-0.38	-0.84 to 0.07	0.099
Male sex	-1.21	-11.85 to 9.43	0.820
Stoma present	-1.41	-20.03 to 17.20	0.879
Rectal surgery (vs colon surgery)	0.68	-12.92 to 14.28	0.920
Adjuvant chemotherapy	3.43	-9.90 to 16.75	0.607
Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy	5.04	-14.40 to 24.48	0.604

To more comprehensively assess factors associated with 3.67, 95% CI 1.10–12.25, $p = 0.035$). No significant impaired quality of life, Global Health Status scores were association was observed for gender, stoma status, surgical binary using a threshold of 70 points. Multivariate logistic category, adjuvant chemotherapy, or neoadjuvant regression analysis showed that being 65 years of age or older chemoradiotherapy. (Table 5) was independently associated with lower quality of life (OR

Table 5. Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of Poor Quality of Life

Variable	OR	95% CI	p value
Age ≥ 65 years	3.67	1.10–12.25	0.035
Male sex	1.16	0.35–3.87	0.810
Stoma present	3.41	0.31–37.45	0.316
Rectal surgery (vs colon surgery)	0.90	0.20–4.05	0.890
Adjuvant chemotherapy	1.10	0.25–4.81	0.902
Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy	0.17	0.01–2.04	0.161

DISCUSSION

In this study, health-related quality of life (HRQoL) was assessed in patients who underwent colorectal cancer surgery using the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire, and factors associated with global health status were identified.

The mean Global Health Status (GHS) score in our cohort was 66.0 ± 18.8 ; this value is consistent with previously reported values among colorectal cancer survivors. In a recent population-based study, Marcos-Delgado and colleagues reported that long-term colorectal cancer survivors generally maintained a moderate-to-good quality of life, despite a persistent symptom burden, particularly fatigue and gastrointestinal dysfunction⁸. Similarly, Pate and colleagues have shown that, although physical and psychosocial limitations may persist for years after treatment, most colorectal cancer survivors achieve an acceptable quality of life⁵. Our findings support the growing body of evidence that successful oncological treatment can be accompanied by satisfactory long-term outcomes, as reported by patients.

Among the functional scales, cognitive functioning received the highest scores, while emotional functioning received the lowest scores. This trend has also been reported in previous studies on colorectal cancer survivors. Emotional functioning is generally negatively affected by fear of recurrence, anxiety related to follow-up examinations, uncertainty regarding prognosis, and concerns about body image related to treatment¹².

Recent studies emphasize that psychological distress can persist even in patients who have recovered from their illness and can significantly affect long-term quality of life, regardless of oncological outcomes¹³. For this reason, survivorship programs should include routine psychological assessments in addition to traditional oncological follow-up.

Fatigue accounted for the most prominent symptom burden in our cohort. Cancer-related fatigue remains one of the most commonly reported long-term symptoms following colorectal cancer treatment and is consistently associated with a decline in quality of life^{14,15}. The underlying mechanisms are multifactorial and include chronic inflammation, reduced physical activity, nutritional deficiencies, sleep disturbances, and psychological stress¹⁶. Therefore, the high fatigue scores observed in our study appear consistent with the current literature.

One of the most important findings of this study was the association between advanced age and low quality of life. Patients aged 65 and older had statistically significantly lower general health status scores, and multivariate logistic regression analysis identified advanced age as an independent predictor of low quality of life. Similar findings have been reported in numerous recent studies. In an analysis of colorectal cancer survivors, Downing et al. found that older patients had statistically significantly lower scores in terms of physical functioning and quality of life compared to younger individuals⁴. Similarly, a recent study demonstrated that advanced age is independently associated with worsened

quality of life outcomes and reduced functional recovery following colorectal cancer treatment¹⁷. Our findings further support the need for age-specific supportive interventions during the postoperative follow-up period.

The findings of the multivariate analyses further reinforce the observed association between age and quality of life. Although age was not found to be statistically significant in the linear regression model that assessed Health Status as a continuous variable ($p=0.099$), a clear trend toward a decline in quality of life with increasing age was observed. More importantly, when quality of life was classified using a binary cutoff of 70 points for General Health Status, multivariate logistic regression analysis revealed that being 65 years of age or older was an independent predictor of low quality of life (OR 3.67; 95% CI 1.10–12.25; $p=0.035$). This finding indicates that the negative effect of age on quality of life persists even after adjusting for potential confounding factors such as gender, stoma status, surgical procedure, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy. Similar observations have been reported in recent survival studies; in these studies, advanced age has consistently emerged as a significant determinant of long-term outcomes reported by patients following colorectal cancer treatment^{5,17,18}.

In particular, none of the treatment-related variables included in the multivariate models were able to independently predict quality of life. Stoma formation, surgical category, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy were all associated with estimates of effect that were not statistically significant. These findings suggest that patient-related factors, particularly age, may have a greater impact on long-term quality of life outcomes than treatment-related characteristics. The absence of an independent association with treatment variables may also reflect advances in perioperative care, modern stoma management, accelerated recovery protocols, and personalized oncological treatment strategies; all of which may reduce the long-term impact of treatment on daily functioning and overall well-being.

The impact of stoma formation on quality of life remains a subject of debate. Historically, a permanent stoma has been associated with a distorted body image, reduced social functioning, and psychological distress¹⁹. However, recent evidence suggests that advances in stoma care, patient

education, and multidisciplinary support have significantly improved adaptation to living with a stoma. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis by Díaz-Sánchez and colleagues reported that, although ostomy patients may experience impairments in specific areas of quality of life, differences in quality of life scores are generally less pronounced than previously believed³. Consistent with these findings, we did not observe a significant association between the presence of an ostomy and global health status. This may indicate that stoma patients today have successfully adapted and that structured postoperative support programs are effective.

Similarly, in our study, neither adjuvant chemotherapy nor neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy had a significant effect on quality of life outcomes. Although systemic treatments may negatively affect quality of life during the active treatment period, previous studies have shown a significant improvement following completion of treatment. Ziętańska and Małgorzewicz recently reported that many chemotherapy-related impairments resolve over time and have limited long-term effects on the quality of life of colorectal cancer survivors⁹. Furthermore, today's neoadjuvant treatment protocols are becoming increasingly individualized, which has the potential to reduce treatment-related long-term morbidity²⁰. The absence of significant differences in our cohort likely reflects the long-term adaptation observed following the completion of multimodal therapy.

Interestingly, no significant difference was observed among patients who underwent surgery for colon and rectal cancer. Historically, rectal cancer surgery has been associated with poorer functional outcomes due to bowel dysfunction, low anterior resection syndrome, and higher stoma rates²¹. However, recent advances in total mesorectal excision techniques, minimally invasive surgery, accelerated recovery programs, and multidisciplinary care have reduced these differences²². In this study, no significant difference in quality of life scores was observed between patients who underwent surgery for colon and rectal cancer. Although rectal cancer survivors frequently experience bowel dysfunction and low anterior resection syndrome, recent advances in surgical techniques, perioperative care, and survivorship programs may have contributed to the reduction in differences in quality of life outcomes between surgical groups²¹.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional design of the study prevents the assessment of temporal changes in quality of life and makes it impossible to draw causal inferences. Second, the relatively small sample size and single-center study setting may limit the generalizability of the findings and reduce statistical power for subgroup analyses. Third, since preoperative quality of life data were not available, a direct comparison between preoperative and postoperative outcomes could not be made. Several potentially relevant variables—such as the burden of comorbidities, frailty status, socioeconomic factors, educational level, postoperative complications, and the time elapsed since surgery—were not included in the multivariate analyses. These factors may independently influence quality of life and may partially explain the variability observed among patients.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable, real-world data on health-related quality of life following colorectal cancer surgery. The use of a validated international questionnaire and the assessment of both surgical and oncological factors reinforce the clinical significance of the findings.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, patients undergoing colorectal cancer surgery demonstrated generally satisfactory quality-of-life outcomes while maintaining their global health status and cognitive function. Among the factors evaluated, advanced age emerged as the most significant determinant of impaired quality of life, showing an independent association with poor quality-of-life outcomes in multivariate analysis. In contrast, factors such as stoma formation, the type of surgical procedure, adjuvant chemotherapy, and neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy did not show a significant association with global health status. These findings suggest that patient-specific factors—particularly age—may have a greater impact on long-term quality of life than treatment-related characteristics. Prospective studies involving larger patient cohorts and long-term follow-up are needed to better define the factors influencing survival and quality-of-life outcomes following colorectal cancer surgery.

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